

CUREX
SECURE AND PRIVATE HEALTH DATA EXCHANGE

CUREX PLATFORM: AN OVERVIEW

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CUREX Fact Sheet

Aim

CUREX is a 40-month Research and Innovation Action (RIA) from 2018 to 2022 funded under Horizon 2020 aimed at producing a novel, flexible and scalable cyber risk management platform designed to protect healthcare data, especially when it is exchanged between healthcare organisations.

How

- By performing cybersecurity and privacy risk assessments.
- By offering optimal recommendations for cyber risk mitigation in the form of a decision support tool.
- By leveraging the blockchain technology to provide accountability and auditability for data transactions, building trust.
- By improving the cyber hygiene culture among personnel.

Pilots

- Data exchange for cross-border patient mobility
- Data exchange in remote healthcare services
- Data exchange for healthcare research

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Consortium

- 17 participants from 9 EU countries
- 7 x research institutes and universities
- 2 x healthcare representatives
- 2 x large industries
- 6 x SMEs

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Executive Summary

The evolution of healthcare delivery has been greatly facilitated by the development of Electronic Health Records (EHR). EHR transformed the healthcare industry from a paper-based system to one that utilises the advantage of the new technologies in order to provide better services. Thinking of EHR as the digital equivalent of a real-time patient paper chart record, it becomes apparent that it will reach its full potential only when it becomes instantly shareable with authorised users, e.g., healthcare providers in a remote location that need access to a patient's medical history in order to effectively treat them. This however, apart from numerous advantages, raises numerous concerns. Most of said concerns are related to the violation of the security and privacy of patients' health data, since all digital assets are prone to cyber-attacks. End-user errors, zero-day vulnerabilities and new exploits can render the safety mechanisms implemented by healthcare organisations obsolete, leading to data leaks or even to data manipulation incidents, endangering both patients' privacy and health.

Cyber criminals are highly attracted by the healthcare sector aiming at compromising healthcare data records, which can impact, or even cost, human lives. Adversaries attempt to exploit vulnerabilities created due to changes in the traditional healthcare treatments, which have been evolved thanks to the advances of the medical technologies. The latter are a double-edged sword offering several new capabilities and opportunities to improve patients' experience and prolong their lives, while relying on software and hardware components which may turn them into prey for cyber criminals.

The above call for a reform of healthcare services and the way we secure the underlying IT infrastructures. In this paper we present how CUREX, a comprehensive cybersecurity risk management platform specifically designed for healthcare organisations under the EU H2020 framework, can help safeguard the IT infrastructures that healthcare services rely upon, such as the health data exchange. To this end, we first outline the components of the CUREX Platform along with functionalities that are carried out by each of them. Then, we proceed describing the use case scenarios against which CUREX is being tested and validated as part of the project's pilots, and we provide an example of usage for the CUREX Platform using the cross-border health data exchange use case scenario. Next, we discuss how CUREX can help healthcare organisations become compliant with the applicable regulatory framework, and finally we share how stakeholders can access the project results.

1. Introduction

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic has severely impacted all sectors worldwide. Among the most affected is inarguably healthcare, forced towards a revolution that has been long overdue. Even before that, healthcare institutions were facing major challenges coping with digitisation, the increased demands of vulnerable populations, such as elders and people with chronic conditions, the real-time tracking of their patients, and of course, the very strict regulatory framework that governs the domain. Yet, the manifestation of the recent pandemic was believed by many to be the tipping point for healthcare delivery to overcome these challenges and transform, in order to conform to the new era which requires increased connectivity [1] (e.g., 5G, IoT) and handling massive sets of data [2], [3]. This has led healthcare organisations to expand their digital infrastructures by incorporating components that support the integration with personal medical devices, ultimately creating the the Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) [4], [5]. This shift, however, also expands the attack surface, adding to the already high incentives cyber attackers have for targeting the domain [6], [7].

It is no secret that the number of cybersecurity incidents reported in healthcare increases every year, and that the domain remains the most targeted one for the past decade [8], [9]. Adversaries, motivated by all those characteristics that make healthcare an alluring target, saw the chaotic situation the pandemic brought as the perfect opportunity for personal gain. As a result, during the same period, healthcare breach costs surged at \$9.23 million per incident, experiencing a \$2 million increase over the previous year [10]. To avoid long operational disruptions and paying huge fines due to privacy violations caused by the hacking attacks, medical institutions have been spending annually a significant deal of their budget on cybersecurity [11]. Nevertheless, these investments may be in vain since in some cases medical IT systems may be outdated [12] and replacing them would be a very slow process, given the criticality of their operations. Therefore, instead of replacing legacy systems, healthcare decision-makers and budget holders seek to invest in cybersecurity solutions that operate on top of their existing infrastructures, reinforcing their security levels [13], [14].

One such solution that is aimed at addressing the cybersecurity issues that arise from the digital evolution of healthcare services and infrastructures is CUREX [15]. Developed within the homonymous EU-funded project, CUREX is a novel, flexible and situational awareness-oriented platform designed specifically to safeguard the confidentiality, integrity and availability of health data. It protects the health data handled by hospitals from the risks that are propagated all the way from the security gaps in their IT infrastructure. CUREX achieves that by implementing a risk-based approach, performing continuous cybersecurity and privacy risk assessments, while also offering optimal recommendations for cyber risk mitigations in the form of a decision support tool. The platform encompasses a suite of tools establishing trust between healthcare organisations to accommodate the necessity of exchanging data in a fully GDPR-compliant manner. By capitalising on existing distributed ledger and health technological artifacts, CUREX ensures the accountability and auditability of all transactions between hospitals and care centres. Finally, taking into account the human factor, it improves the cyber hygiene culture among personnel through identifying employee group-specific gaps and needs with regard to raising cybersecurity and data privacy awareness.

2. Architecture and Main Technological Areas

The core of the CUREX project is to evaluate the privacy and cybersecurity risk to which healthcare infrastructures are exposed while exchanging data with other healthcare centres and third-party organizations. This is admittedly one of the most critical needs for the healthcare domain today due the proliferation of the IoMT, the always growing need for improving healthcare research based on available data, and the increasing mobility of patients within EU borders. During bi-directional communications, every open port required for the transmission of data from one endpoint to another increases the organisation's chances of being breached [16]. CUREX focuses on ensuring the confidentiality, integrity and availability of health data by protecting the organisation against novel threats and risks that arise from the data exchange process, where the hospital IT infrastructure is directly connected to another medical facility that might be compromised.

Risk-based security frameworks have been found to be ideally positioned for healthcare since they apply a proactive approach that can comprehensively address the emerging security gaps, while taking into account the organisation processes and workflows [17], [18]. Cybersecurity risk management begins with identifying potential risks threatening specific vulnerable assets. Based on the likelihood of an attack, its possible impact and the countermeasures implemented to reduce it, the risk assessment procedure estimates the risk score values for the organisation. After that, a mitigation plan is prepared for the organisation to carry out before reinitiating the risk management procedure to see how the risk score values have been improved.

CUREX realises the traditional risk management process by implementing a number of capabilities including asset and vulnerability discovery, threat detection, cybersecurity and privacy risk assessments, and recommendation of optimal safeguards strategies. After the risk management process has been concluded, the outputs (i.e., cybersecurity and privacy risk scores, list of recommended mitigation controls) are published on a decentralized blockchain infrastructure for accountability and auditability purposes, that guarantees their integrity and immutability. As CUREX proposes a GDPR-compliant, holistic risk management approach for healthcare organisations, it cannot afford to disregard the significant role end-users play in the security equation. Hence, going beyond the technical means described earlier, we include user training and awareness strategies as part of the CUREX cyber hygiene framework to also strengthen the healthcare organisations' defences against social attacks.

FIGURE 1. CUREX FRAMEWORK STACK

In Figure 1 we present the complete CUREX framework stack divided in strategic areas, each comprising one or more tools based on their functionality and purpose. These tools have been combined under a flexible, modular and agile architecture as depicted in Figure 2 [19]. In the remaining of this section, we briefly outline the functionalities carried out by the individual tools, whereas in section 4 we analyse how these work together in the cross-border health data exchange scenario implemented in the framework of Use Case 1.

FIGURE 2. CUREX ARCHITECTURE

2.1 Asset and Vulnerability Discovery

This module is composed by the Asset Discovery tool (ADT) [20], [21] and the Vulnerability Discovery Manager (VDM) [22], [23], whose goal is to discover system assets (e.g., components, services, applications, ports, OS) and any information related to their associated vulnerabilities. ADT receives network traffic and produces as output information about such a network, including information of specific components that conform the network (assets) and their characteristics (services, ports, etc.). The aim of the ADT in the CUREX framework environment is to discover devices within a hospital local network and gather as much information as possible from these devices, in order to allow other tools of the CUREX framework to work with the obtained data.

Every time a new asset is discovered by the ADT or whenever there is a change in the system's configuration, a vulnerability analysis will be performed by the VDM. VDM is a domain specific tool for identifying, analysing and reporting vulnerabilities detected in the target system at different layers. In CUREX, VDM covers the identification, classification and prioritization of system resources, the definition of remediation solutions for strategies to cover the vulnerabilities, and the adoption of intelligence sharing functionalities to share information among hospitals and healthcare centres. As a result, the output of this module enables the discovery of possible attack spaces, adversarial models and will feed the threat intelligence module, where all threats are compiled in an online dossier.

2.2 Threat Intelligence

This module is composed by the Knowledge Extraction and Analytics (KEA) [24], [25] and the Threat Intelligence Engine (TIE) [26] that apply advanced machine learning algorithms and artificial intelligence techniques for the detection of real time abnormal behaviours on users, and devices, as well as anomalies in the data in order to identify new and unknown threats. KEA deals with the application of machine learning and broader data analytics methodologies to develop classification models for

revealing vulnerabilities and profiling threats that have not been discovered by the previous module. It encapsulates outlier detection based on unsupervised learning, performs audit log analytics and data preparations, and develops techniques that can be employed for early threat detection.

TIE is responsible for the analysis of all threat-related information obtained from the target system at different levels and the (close) to real-time detection of imminent threats, paying particular attention to the safety of data and their exchange with other organisations. The information being analysed includes known vulnerabilities, past incidents, network traffic and system logs which will be monitored in order to timely identify suspicious behaviours and produce alerts. TIE has in-built SIEM capabilities (provided by the XL-SIEM component [27]) which allows for correlating threat-related data from multiple sources and raising security alarms with an associated severity level.

2.3 Cyber Risk Management

The Cyber Risk Management module [28] is composed of the Cybersecurity Assessment Tool (CAT) [29], the Privacy Assessment Tool (PAT) [30] as well as the Optimal Safeguards Tool (OST) [31] aiming to produce risk scores and optimal mitigation measures towards a cyber strategy of the healthcare organisation.

CAT focuses on collecting and analysing cybersecurity events in real time and consolidating a correlation of them for a risk assessment. This latter is done together with the e-health business profile (e.g., critical elements, minimum set of functionalities to be provided, impact in the system and services of the threats, etc.). PAT provides healthcare organizations with the appropriate privacy levels in complete alignment with the GDPR directives to protect patients' Personal Identifiable Information (PII) and sensitive clinical data [32]. Both risk assessments are performed by contrasting static vulnerability analysis (provided by VDM), with real time SIEM analysis (provided by TIE) to support known and zero-day vulnerabilities and attacks.

The Optimal Safeguards Tool (OST) determines and visualises optimal combinations of cybersecurity safeguards to protect healthcare organisations. The real-world safeguards selected, analysed and used in OST are mainly the Critical Internet Security (CIS) Critical Security Controls against major attack types mitigated by these Controls. OST is equipped with capabilities for splitting a cybersecurity budget into the different controls while maximising the degree of risk mitigation. The outcome of this module are optimal cybersecurity and privacy safeguards that will help security managers (e.g., CIOs, CISOs) decide about optimal portfolios of these safeguards to mitigate and control risk in an optimal way. CUREX provides an innovative decision support method with a list of controls (using the well-known CIS controls) that healthcare organizations can implement for risk control. This service does not implement any safeguards, but it selects optimal strategies, from a list of controls such as CIS controls, for a particular organisation and threat scenario [33].

For every risk model, a list of potential mitigation measures is suggested to be implemented by the healthcare organization aiming to reduce the risk levels to acceptable levels. Mitigation measures are prioritized based on multiple factors such as purchase and implementation cost, usability costs, and security benefits, which are reflected on the degree of improvement of risk when a mitigation measure is used by a system.

Please note that this process does not involve enforcing any mitigation measures; it focuses on cyber risk assessments and providing advice and guidelines to security administrators and C-level managers to define mitigation strategies based on the computed scores.

2.4 Trust Enhancing

This module consists of a Private Blockchain (PrB) deployment that stores data related to the requests made for health records, enhancing traceability of transactions and trust. The CUREX PrB [34], [35], implemented using the Hyperledger Fabric open source blockchain technology, enables auditability, accountability, traceability, and leverages the smart contracts technology for the purposes of the healthcare domain. CUREX uses PrB to record (i) the cybersecurity and privacy risk scores derived by the analysis performed by the risk assessment toolkit, comprising CAT and PAT, (ii) a subset of the OST results to act as a reference point in case of a cyber incident to audit whether the organisation has implemented safeguards in alignment with the platform recommendations, and (iii) the transactions occurred among stakeholders.

2.5 Application and Visualisation

This module consists of the Patient Application (PA) and the Health Professional Application (HPA) [36], as well as the CUREX Visualisation Tool (CVT). The applications aim to interact with the CUREX platform to evaluate and analyse the possible risks associated with the data sharing process and display them in a synthesized way. More specifically, the Patient Application (PA) is a mobile application that provides data owners (patients) the necessary control over their health data, according to the GDPR. The PA complements health data exchange through the CUREX Platform and its components by enabling data owners to review and define the way their data is handled through providing their informed consent.

The Health Professional Application (HPA) is the interaction point for health professionals to create and validate data transactions between stakeholders and/or services. Each transaction is stored in the Private Blockchain. Transactions contain necessary information about the exchange details (e.g., requirements between parties), along with cybersecurity and privacy context (i.e., risk information) as provided by the CUREX risk assessment module. When the transaction is validated across the CUREX network through the Private Blockchain, the request is sent to the corresponding HPA of the hospital. The HPA's feature of recording transactions to the Private Blockchain provides auditability functionalities and feedback to the CUREX assessment tools with dynamic recalculation of the security and privacy risk scores. Transactions initiated by the HPA will have the cyber and privacy scores validated by a smart contract executed in the Private Blockchain.

The CUREX Visualization Tool (CVT) provides visualization functionalities along with the possibility, for the users, to select the element(s) to be displayed in the CVT dashboard. As such, CUREX users have the possibility of displaying individual or combined visualization aspects from one or several elements from the CUREX solution.

2.6 Human-centric Cyber Hygiene

Cyber hygiene (CH) is a fundamental principle relating to information security and is the equivalent of establishing simple routine measures to minimise the risks from cyber threats and recently, it has emerged as one of the most efficient ways to prevent accidental human errors [37], [38]. The traditional industrial practice to enhance security posture by utilizing IT security-biased protection methods narrowly focuses on improving cyber hygiene and individual component protection [39].

In CUREX, we propose a survey-based risk assessment methodology [40] for recommending optimal human-centric controls to manage various human-related cybersecurity and data privacy risks based on the identified risk strategy. The results of the assessment process feed the CUREX Cyber Risk Management module, identifying weak behaviour patterns associated with the human factor and promoting activities to raise cybersecurity and privacy awareness.

The CH methodology comprises the following steps (Figure 3):

- Extract knowledge and assess the needs and gaps of different employee groups at healthcare organisations through a survey questionnaire;
- Process and analyse the participants' responses;
- Identify the most effective strategy to address each cybersecurity and data privacy risk;
- Recommend targeted human-centric controls to implement the strategy;
- The management team can apply the controls to the workforce to improve the situation.

FIGURE 3. CYBER HYGIENE METHODOLOGY

3. Pilot Use Cases

3.1 Data exchange in remote healthcare services (Use case 2)

Patient-centric, networked care and increased involvement of patients in their own care accelerates the need for secure data collection, transmission and communication outside hospitals, and specifically between healthcare organisations and patients. For such remote healthcare services, data is collected from a variety of different, often mobile, modalities, thus requiring a high level of security and privacy for data entry, transmission, and storage of the sensitive, personal data. For clinical research, similar infrastructures are needed as more and more research data is collected remotely from patients.

In this use case, the risk assessment capabilities of CUREX are evaluated in two different settings:

- In an IoT Healthcare Platform.
- In a Point-of-Care (POC) System.

The first one has been piloted using the platform service for managing research studies related to the remote collection of health data and interaction with patients, which is part of the research infrastructure of the Karolinska Institutet medical university in Sweden. The service consists of a mobile application for smartphone or tablet transmitting information, via a secure connection, to a secure server which is hosted at the medical university. Care professionals access the data through a web interface for clinical monitoring of patient reported outcomes. The patient is the user of the mobile application (patient app), while the care professionals are the users of the web application. Research administrators use a web interface for surveillance and management of several ongoing research studies.

In medical research, safe and GDPR compliant data management is of utmost importance. The deployment of the CUREX Platform enables IT administrators to survey the security of the underlying infrastructure inside the medical university in depth. CUREX allows for detecting the vulnerable assets, as well as intrusion attempts against the network. Based on the findings, it calculates the cybersecurity and privacy risk scores of the system, quantifying the total risk the infrastructure is exposed to, at any given moment. If the risk is high, the IT administrator is prompted to apply the mitigation controls proposed by the platform in order to lower the risk and ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of health data.

In the second setting, the emphasis is shifted towards evaluating CUREX in a Healthcare Point of Care (POC) System and promoting cyber hygiene in such a setting. Healthcare POC systems have been widely used in hospitals in order to provide innovative solutions to medical professionals and physicians and provide them with an overview of the patients' condition in a way that makes it easier for them to respond on time and prevent critical situations. POC systems are platforms that incorporate medical devices and applications in order to collect, process and visualise data. Naturally, these types of platforms create an expanded attack surface, as the variety of devices and systems used have unique vulnerabilities, which may be more challenging to identify and address. As large amounts of data, which contain personal identifiable information (PII) and sensitive medical data, is being communicated across various devices or sensors, backend analytical platforms, and user workstations or smartphones, it becomes evident that there are multiple threats that may cause data leakages or breach incidents. Hospitals and care centres need to address this challenge by efficiently assessing the associated risks and mitigate them with the proper cybersecurity safeguards.

Use Case 2b has been tested with the participation of health professionals from the Fundació Privada Hospital Asil de Granollers, Spain, further evaluating CUREX's impact on data exchange in healthcare services. Contrary to the previous scenarios, the focus is on modelling and analysing the infrastructure with POCs. This is done with a view to deriving risk assessment scores related to privacy and cybersecurity, as well as recommendations about optimal safeguards to be adopted so that the overall cybersecurity and risk levels are lowered. Within this sub-use case, three test scenarios have been demonstrated: (i) Scenario 1: Access to documents and images results in a very high combined cybersecurity and privacy risk score; (ii) Scenario 2: Access through mobile app results in a medium combined cybersecurity and privacy risk score; and (iii) Scenario 3: Communication of simulated clinical data results in a low combined cybersecurity and privacy risk score. Overall, the results obtained during the successful demonstrations indicated that all the CUREX achieves its functional and technical objectives.

3.2 Data exchange for cross-border patient mobility (Use case 1)

The transfer of Electronic Health Records (EHR) is an everyday growing need for Health personnel, especially doctors, it could even be "a matter of life or death", as stated by various physician participants.

Aware of this, the Spanish health ministry has launched or collaborated with various initiatives to share EHRs. In the community of Madrid there is Historia Clínica Electrónica Única y Centralizada (HORUS) that shares EHRs with any health centre of the community. In Spain Historia Nacional (HCDSNS) is almost 100% operational sharing EHRs nationwide and in Europe the eHealth Digital Service Infrastructure (eHDSI) initiative will share EHRs with all EU member state health centres. CUREX can help harden and improve the cybersecurity aspects of the process, by ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, availability, and accountability in the system, while maintaining compliance with the GDPR. By securing health data transfers, healthcare organisations can elevate their trust levels required for sharing of health data in Europe, for both medical and research purposes.

This use case ties together and demonstrates, with a simple proof-of-concept that hides the underlying complexity to the end-users, all the CUREX tools under a user-friendly interface for medical staff and patients. Use Case 1 depends directly on the success of Use Case 2 described earlier that assesses the successful outcome of the CUREX Risk Management, i.e.: the transfer of medical data must be supported by cyber secure platforms. CUREX combines a series of tools that identify and assess the cybersecurity and privacy risks for the IT of health centres together with the blockchain technology, where each health centre publishes its cyber security and privacy status with a simple risk score that varies from very low to very high. CUREX is also situational aware, meaning that the risk score elevates when the health centre is under a cyberattack or if a new vulnerability is disclosed. This way, all CUREX health centres are always aware of the risk scores of other health centres and can decide whether it's safe for them to communicate in order to exchange data or not. After evaluating the risk scores of health centres before exchanging health data, the assessed risk scores and corresponding data transfer operations are ledged on the blockchain to guarantee data integrity and most importantly, non-repudiation.

The use case has been validated and accepted by medical and IT personnel from the Hospital Universitario Puerta de Hierro Majadahonda in Spain and the Karolinska Institutet in Sweden. Overall, CUREX was endorsed by the end-users as a reliable and verifiable cybersecurity solution towards building the “Circle of Trust” that is essential for the secure health data transfer and collaboration between European member states.

3.3 Data exchange for healthcare research (Use case 3)

Managing and assessing the risks of data exchanges becomes a very complex task when the data is related to healthcare. Pioneering work on data exchange for healthcare research was done by the MyHealthMyData (MHMD)¹ H2020 project. In this regard, MHMD proposed an innovative way to facilitate such exchanges by relying on a blockchain network to govern the data sharing life cycle (from the initial request done by a researcher to the transfer of the corresponding datasets) in a secure and trusted manner. For the purposes of Use case 3, CUREX is integrated with the MHMD network, providing it with risk assessment capabilities. More specifically, by operating as a parallel blockchain network, CUREX provides support for the evaluation of privacy risks of MHMD organisations that participate on data exchanges. Moreover, by having CUREX evaluate the privacy risks associated with a particular data package, it supports the decision-making process of MHMD organisations regarding data exchanges. Therefore, by combining the two of them, CUREX contributes to improving the data exchange model in MHMD.

www.myhealthmydata.eu/

To achieve the use cases objectives, the CUREX's PrB and PAT tools were developed to support the integration between both platforms. In order to test and validate the results, two pilots (Fundación Privada Hospital Asil de Granollers and Karolinska Institutet) participated to run the use case scenarios.

4. Example of usage: Cross-border health data exchange with the CUREX Platform

In this section, we demonstrate how the CUREX platform interacts in the event of a patient traveling abroad who needs to visit a hospital due to an emergency. The key objective of this scenario, which is one of the three use cases where CUREX is being validated, is to consolidate the strong foundations of our solution in real-world demands with a focus on facilitating seamless, secure, private, and traceable workflow for the end-users. The use case pilot has been deployed in two different health providers' infrastructures, in environments that have been simulated but remain realistic. The originating health provider (Hospital A) is the Hospital Universitario Puerta de Hierro Majadahonda (HUPHM) in Spain, and the destination health provider (Hospital B) is in Sweden, simulated in the infrastructure of Karolinska Institutet (KI) (see Figure 4). For the scenario, we consider a Spanish citizen with a chronic condition who is spending time in Sweden. Her doctor in Spain prompts her to visit the local Swedish clinic, after noticing signs of deterioration based on her vital measurements. The patient visits the Hospital B's outpatient service, where she is initially administered for examination.

FIGURE 4. CROSS-BORDER HEALTH DATA EXCHANGE SCENARIO

The healthcare professional (i.e., usually a physician, or a nurse) assigned to the case as well as the patient are both registered CUREX users. The patient informs the healthcare professional about her chronic condition and the healthcare professional asks to get access to her EHR in order to give a proper diagnosis and treatment. The healthcare professional logs into his HPA using his credentials and searches within CUREX for the patient using as unique identifier her Patient Identification Number (PIN), available on her European Health Insurance Card (EHIC). Once the patient is found in CUREX, the healthcare professional fills in the respective "medical performance scenario" field, indicating where the patient is currently being cared for. Apart from the details related to the patient's ID and the performance scenario, no other data is allowed to be entered to the request to avoid having Personal Identifiable Information being exposed, violating the GDPR. Finally, the EHR request is launched by the HPA.

At this point, we assume that both hospitals have performed the complete risk management procedure, leveraging for this purpose the functionalities offered by the CUREX tools. We briefly outline the flow between them below (see Figure 5):

- During the *Asset and Vulnerability Discovery* process, we have the ADT scan the underlying IT infrastructure and produce a list with the assets, along with their characteristics (i.e., operating system, IP address, open ports). VDM then receives the list and performs the vulnerability analysis, reporting on the security vulnerabilities found per asset (Steps 1-2).
- The list of vulnerabilities is later shared with the *Threat Intelligence* group of tools (namely, KEA and TIE), to implement the threat detection. More specifically, KEA analyses the vulnerability list using ML-based techniques focusing on misuse and anomaly detection, to identify new threat patterns against the hospital systems. KEA then returns its findings to VDM which produces an enhanced version of the vulnerability report, which it forwards to the TIE module. TIE correlates the reported results with logs obtained from different sensors in the network, to reveal suspicious events taking place (Steps 3-4).
- The *Cyber Risk Management* module initiates the risk assessment process by feeding the enriched vulnerability results to the CAT and PAT tools (Steps 5-6). CAT, receiving also as input the list of suspicious events produced by TIE (Step 5), performs the cybersecurity risk assessment and generates risk scores. The same applies to PAT, which performs the privacy risk assessment, estimating the corresponding privacy risk score and assessing the level of GDPR compliance of the organisation. CAT proposes mitigation controls that are sent to OST for further analysis and optimisation based on their monetary values and efficiency (Step 7). The risk scores by CAT and PAT, as well as a subset of the OST recommendations, are then published on the PrB (Step 8). A new risk assessment procedure can be initiated by the end-users after the implementation of the mitigation controls proposed by OST, or due to changes in the underlying infrastructure (i.e., the addition of new assets) of the healthcare organisation (Step 9).

FIGURE 5. INTERACTIONS BETWEEN THE CUREX TOOLS

PAT	Very High	M	H	H	VH	VH
	High	L	M	H	H	VH
	Medium	L	L	M	H	H
	Low	VL	L	L	M	H
	Very Low	VL	VL	L	L	M
		Very Low	Low	Medium	High	Very High
		CAT				

FIGURE 6. MATRIX USED TO CALCULATE THE ORGANISATION JOINT RISK SCORE

As soon as HPA notifies about the EHR transfer request, the PrB takes over. Figure 7 presents the interaction flow between PrB, the HPA, the PA and the two hospitals. After the initialisation of the transfer request (Step 1), PrB merges the CAT and PAT scores reported for Hospital A into a global organisation risk score named joint score, using the CUREX smart contracts and the matrix presented in Figure 5, and then, it proceeds to examine whether the joint score is within the predefined acceptable range (Step 2). In case the joint risk score of the requested hospital is above the threshold, the transfer is aborted, the physician gets notified that the procedure has failed due to security reasons and the use case scenario is concluded. If the joint risk score is found to be suitable according to the organisations' pre-established policies, the PrB checks whether the request has been marked as an emergency (Step 3). For the emergency scenario, we consider that the patient is not in position to provide her consent and authorise the transfer, due to either being admitted to the hospital unconscious, or with a physical/mental impairment. In that case, we accelerate the process, bypassing the patient consent step to move on to the treatment. The hospital that makes use of the emergency option has to comply with the terms and conditions that may require them to justify their action at a later stage.

FIGURE 7. CUREX PRB WORKFLOW DIAGRAM

If the request is not an emergency case, the PrB instance of the requesting hospital (KI) sends a notification to the patient's PA with the details pertaining to the request, such as the healthcare professional who submitted it, his medical specialty and the institution he represents. The patient is given the option to "Accept" or "Reject" the transfer (Step 4). As soon as she accepts the request, the EHR transfer mechanism is prompted by CUREX, providing the Spanish hospital with the necessary information needed to search for the patient's EHR in the local HIS (Step 5). Then, the transfer process takes place, extracting the patient's EHR from the originating health centre (HUPHM) and sending it to the destination facility (KI). At this point, we should mention that the EHR transfer process is out of scope for CUREX, and it is realised by means agreed between the exchanging parties.

Once KI receives the patient's EHR in the simulated environment, CUREX is notified about the successful transfer (Step 6). CUREX, in turn, will send a notification to the physician's HPA informing that the patient's EHR is now available, and that he can proceed to treat the patient (Step 7). Finally, the log data pertaining to the healthcare professional's EHR request (realised through the HPA), the patient's consent (provided using the PA), and the system operations required to complete the transaction are stored on the PrB with the corresponding cybersecurity and privacy scores that were applicable at the time. The PII's of healthcare professionals and patients are stored in a database parallel to the PrB, to avoid having them stored on the blockchain. A complete trace can be retrieved by joining the existing hash codes in both databases. Not including PII's in the PrB is in accordance with the GDPR and most importantly, with the provisions of Art. 17 "Right to erasure ('right to be forgotten')", because information published on the PrB cannot be altered or deleted.

5. Compliance with the Regulatory Framework

There is a long list of innovative digital solutions that failed to be adopted by healthcare organisations because they do not meet the legal requirements defined for the health sector. Adopting the CUREX platform in a hospital environment necessitates its integration in the regulatory framework these hospitals have to comply with in the domain of cybersecurity. In Europe, this cybersecurity legal framework is evolving rapidly, it is still highly fragmented, and it becomes progressively more complex. When considering the introduction of additional tools to assess and enhance cybersecurity, hospital management will need a response to the question how these additional tools fit in their cybersecurity-related legal duties and how a platform such as CUREX can enhance their potential to comply with these legal duties. Besides technical and organisational assistance, the CUREX offering will, therefore, also include tailored regulatory advice.

The EU Network and Information Security Directive² (EU 2016/1148) has been the first piece of cybersecurity legislation at the Union level. It was adopted in 2016 and subsequently, because it is an EU directive, every EU Member State has started to adopt national legislation transposing this directive. The NIS Directive has three parts:

- National capabilities: EU Member States must have certain national cybersecurity capabilities of the individual EU countries, e.g., they must have a national CSIRT, perform cyber exercises, etc.
- Cross-border collaboration: Cross-border collaboration between EU countries, e.g., the operational EU CSIRT network, the strategic NIS cooperation group, etc.

- National supervision of critical sectors: EU Member States have to supervise the cybersecurity of critical market operators in their country: Ex-ante supervision in critical sectors (energy, transport, water, health, digital infrastructure and finance sector), ex-post supervision for critical digital service providers (online marketplaces, cloud and online search engines).

On 16 December 2020, the Commission and the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy presented a new EU Cybersecurity Strategy³. The Commission’s proposals aim to address both cyber and physical resilience of critical entities and networks: a Directive on measures for high common level of cybersecurity across the Union⁴ (revised NIS Directive or ‘NIS 2’), and a new Directive on the resilience of critical entities⁵. They cover a wide range of sectors such among which the health sector takes a prominent place. The new Commission proposal aims to address the deficiencies of the previous NIS Directive, to adapt it to the current needs and make it future proof.

The fact that the NIS Directive leaves some margin to individual Member States to adapt the European rules to the specific context of their country, has significantly contributed to the complexity in the legal landscape in the EU. For instance, not all Member States have included the health sector in their list of “critical infrastructures” for which stricter rules apply. Yet, offering the CUREX platform to potential customers in the health sector could be facilitated by the fact that such platform can be used, for example, by hospitals to meet the ENISA recommendations [41] for implementing the NIS Directive in the health sector. These recommendations are not binding but provide useful guidance for the health sector. Table 1 lists the good practices proposed by ENISA that are being addressed by the different CUREX components.

² <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2016/1148/oj>.

³ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/eus-cybersecurity-strategy-digital-decade>

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/proposal-directive-measures-high-common-level-cybersecurity-across-union>

⁵ https://ec.europa.eu/home-affairs/sites/homeaffairs/files/pdf/15122020_proposal_directive_resilience_critical_entities_com-2020-829_en.pdf

TABLE 1. RELEVANT ENISA RECOMMENDATIONS AND CUREX COMPONENTS

ENISA’s Good Practices for Cybersecurity	CUREX Component	Functionality
Perform asset inventory	ADT	ADT discovers and lists all assets connected to the IP network of a health institution (healthcare devices, mobiles, workstations, servers, etc.), along with any kind of information on the assets’ operating systems, open ports, etc. that might be susceptible to an attack.
Implement vulnerability management	VDM	VDM, analyses all possible vulnerabilities that can be exploited in the infrastructure. It covers both cybersecurity and privacy vulnerabilities with a particular focus on health data, healthcare information systems and medical devices.

Identify threats	KEA	KEA identifies a set of effective techniques that harvest the knowledge that is extracted from health data sources or network monitoring, in order to reveal vulnerabilities and the profile of threats that target the health system.
	TIE	TIE enables organizations to turn the voluminous and heterogenous threat-related data generated daily by internal and external sources into actionable insights that will help them perceive, reason, learn and defend against cyber-threats.
Conduct risk assessment	CAT	CAT identifies the threats to which a healthcare organization is exposed to during data exchange and assesses its cybersecurity risk level.
	PAT	PAT assesses the privacy risk level of an organisation with the goal to support compliance with the GDPR for protecting patients' privacy.
Allow auditing and logging	PrB	PrB securely logs the following information to an immutable ledger for accountability, traceability, and auditability purposes: (i) the cybersecurity and privacy risk scores derived by the analysis performed by CAT and PAT, (ii) a subset of the OST results, and (iii) the transactions occurred between the stakeholders (i.e., requests made for health records to be exchanged between hospitals).
Raise cybersecurity awareness	CH	Cyber Hygiene, using as main tool a survey, engages different healthcare employee groups, addressing them a series of targeted questions to extract knowledge and understand the group-specific gaps and needs with regards to raising cybersecurity and data privacy awareness.

Healthcare organisations have always been at the centre of attention regarding the application of General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR (EU) Regulation 2016/679). Being GDPR-compliant by design, CUREX:

- i. Enables organisations to apply the GDPR provisions when transferring health records from one medical facility to another by collecting and securely logging the patient's consent.
- ii. Respects the data protection principles during the monitoring of the hospital's underlying IT infrastructure.

CUREX heavily relies on the monitoring and assessment of the underlying IT infrastructure of a healthcare organisation. This monitoring produces metadata regarding IPs and MAC addresses of hardware devices, mentioned as assets. Monitoring the electronic communications of individuals such as the healthcare organisation's patients and employees, triggers the applicability of the GDPR, as this regulation applies to the processing of personal data of EU residents. CUREX respects all the data protection principles, such as the lawfulness, fairness, transparency, data minimisation, and storage limitation. The data models used can validate that the IP and MAC addresses of hardware assets are processed only for the purposes of detecting vulnerabilities and threat patterns, and their storage can be restricted according to the retention policy enforced by the hospital security administrators.

6. CUREX Innovations

Health data exchange introduces new types of threats where privacy violations are more likely to occur. Moreover, the lack of a collectively accepted and auditable exchange record leads to reduced trust between parties. Existing solutions reflect traditional cybersecurity solutions with no added value, their stronger point being the level of maturity as they have entered the market way before CUREX. However, CUREX provides a holistic approach when it comes to cybersecurity solutions in the healthcare sector as it considers and reflects real world problems. More specifically, CUREX provides a cybersecurity risk assessment toolkit tailored to healthcare organisations, infrastructures and services that assesses the compliance with GDPR and ensures that data is processed and exchanged in an appropriate and privacy-aware manner. Moreover, CUREX integrates the developed toolkits and applications into a private blockchain consensus business network implementing smart contracts. The vision of this platform is to safeguard patient privacy and increase their trust in the currently vulnerable critical healthcare information infrastructures, especially in cases where data is exchanged.

CUREX empowers healthcare institutions to assess and address their cybersecurity and privacy risks associated with health data exchange and enhance their cybersecurity and privacy awareness among the organisation personnel, while enabling secure and authorised sensitive health data exchange efficiently, accurately, and effectively.

CUREX does not offer just another cybersecurity generic solution that can be applied on the healthcare sector, as it takes into serious consideration how the healthcare sector operates. Additionally, existing cybersecurity solutions focus on the technology aspects and less on the holistic approach that includes the human factor. CUREX invests on the human factor and their situational awareness while providing a tamper-proof ledger that provides an audit trail with every exchange activity performed on health data. Additionally, one of the most innovative features that makes CUREX unique is the adoption of the blockchain technology which is a system of recording information and works as a digital ledger of transactions that is duplicated and distributed across the entire network of computer systems on the blockchain. Combination of different solutions such as the Optimal Safeguards Tool and Vulnerability Discovery Manager makes the final product very unique as these technologies are innovative and this ensures the highest level of satisfaction to the end users of this solution.

The CUREX Platform proposes innovative solutions to healthcare organisations' challenging efforts in preserving their cybersecurity safeguards. Its market potential is indisputable, as it presents a Unique Value Proposition which is based on an integrated system that combines all CUREX state-of-the-art components. With the use of various market prospects and tools, consortium partners were able to identify the roadmap to sustainability against competitors, adaptability from potential customers, and evolution of the CUREX platform as a novel solution offered to the healthcare security sector. There is a strong commercialisation potential that derives from efforts placed in analysing market access and formulating a concise business plan. With an explicit knowledge of the factors that shape the CUREX market adoption and evolution trends, contributing partners are able to pursue this path of commercialisation and bringing this novel service to the market. Market dynamic and competitive framework of the EU market environment, which is the initial target market, pose both opportunities and restraints that CUREX platform addresses through an intuitive go-to-market plan, coupled with an innovative pricing policy.

Table 2 provides a summary of all the available resources published for the platform as a whole, as well as the individual results of the project. These resources present in detail the R&D, technological and innovation aspects of the individual tools, as well as their go-to-market plan.

Component	Owner	Demo Videos	Deliverables	Publication	Horizon Results Page
CUREX Platform	The CUREX Consortium				
ADT	Universidad Politecnica De Madrid 				
VMD	Atos Spain SA 				
CAT					
KEA	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki 				
TIE	Suite5 Data Intelligence Solutions Limited 				
PAT	Ubitech LTD 				
OST	University of Greenwich 				
PrB	Almerys 				
HPA/PA	Cyberlens BV 				
CH	University of Cyprus 				

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